

Charged Hadron Analysis with the PHENIX Detector

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Abstract

This document details the procedure for analyzing charged track information from the inner tracking system in the PHENIX Detector

1 Introduction

This document will walk you through the introductory steps of analyzing information from the PHENIX tracking systems, focusing on reconstructing charged hadrons. It includes an analysis module that can be downloaded from CVS, built, and used to analyze PHENIX data that is stored in local data files. The output will consist of a TTuple and a number of multidimensional histograms, which pretty much covers the basis of PHENIX analyses. The module will also include a “macros” directory which will contain example code to analyze the 1 and 3 dimensional output histograms, as well as a skeleton with instructions for analyzing the TTuple. The reasoning behind the choice of output formats will be discussed later. This code and demonstration in particular will focus on analyzing information from Run 14’s $Au + Au$ at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200\text{GeV}$ dataset.

2 Charged Track QA

The end game of charged hadron analysis/reconstruction is to, given a sample of charged **tracks**, identify which are high quality enough and have specific kinematics such that they’re most likely charged hadrons (and not electrons, see Roli Esha’s module for that). So, to be super precise, the analysis module analyzes charged *track* information, and, given a series of cuts which I’ll explain in a moment, decides whether or not it’s a charged hadron.

2.1 Event Cuts

For the sake of this demonstration, the event-wide cuts really boil down to just the z vertex of the collision and the centrality, and you’re free to set them as you please. The bulk of the events lie within ± 10 cm for Run 14 for the sake of maximizing VTX usage, so that’s a fine z-vertex cut, and usually we go in increments of 20% for the centrality (e.g. 0-20%, 20-40%, etc.), but if you just want tons and tons of statistics to play around with, you can always make these super wide, say, $|z| < 20\text{cm}$ in the 0-40% centrality bin.

2.2 Charged Track Information

There’s a ton of information contained with a given PHCentralTrack node (see Chris Pinkeburg’s talk on Fun4All if that doesn’t mean anything to you yet), and we only make use of a sliver of it. In this code we look at, per charged track:

- Charge: \pm
- Arm: East/West arms of the central barrel

- Quality: quantifies the number and pattern of wires hit in the drift chamber. See [This page](#) for information on what the different bits mean. Note: you need to be proxied into the BNL network somehow to see these pages.
- ϕ_0, θ_0, z : azimuthal and polar angles and z location (note, this is not the z-vertex).
- p_x and p_y : x and y components of the momentum, respectively.
- n_0 : number of PMT's in the RICH fired.
- pc3dz, pc3dphi and emcdz, emcdphi: quantifies how well tracks reconstructed in the drift chamber point back to associated hits in the pad chamber or emcal. Basically another track quality cut.

Some of these, like the charge and arm information, are there for diagnostics and for what we call “sanity cuts”. Sometimes, a track will return a value of -99 or -9999 for one these entries, typically ones that we don’t cut on (e.g., we accept tracks from either the east or west arm, but we don’t want tracks who don’t know what arm they came from, which might signify something wrong in the rest of their information or in their reconstruction in general).

2.3 Charged Track Cuts

These are the cuts we use on charged tracks when studying two-particle correlations to measure jet modification. They, of course, aren’t limited to this purview.

- Quality: 63 || 31, highest and second to high track qualities
- $n_0 < 0$ for $p_T < 5$ GeV/c, this cut gets rid of electrons in our sample, but above 5GeV/c, hadrons will also fire the RICH, so we turn it off.
- PC3/EMC Circular matching cut: $\sqrt{pc3dphi^2 + pc3dz^2} \leq 2\sigma$. Or replace PC3 with EMC if the pad chamber has a whole in it.

3 Building the Analysis Module

Every analysis module should contain:

- autogen.sh
- Makefile.am
- configure.in
- Module.C
- Module.h
- ModuleLinkDef.h

There may be many a few different .C files (e.g. Module_1.C, Module_2_That_Helps_Module1.C, etc), but this is the bare minimum for a module to compile. Our example module has all these files, to check it out, type:

```
cvs co offline/AnalysisTrain/PHENIXTracking_School_2021
```

Note, this is going to plop down wherever you type it. So if you're in your home directory, fine, now you have a directory called `offline`, which itself has `AnalysisTrain/etc`. If you're in a subdirectory somewhere, you might make a mess.

You'll notice that this tracking module's naming convention is pretty simple: `Hadron_Tracking*`. You can also view this module via the cvs viewer by going to:

```
https://phenix-intra.sdcc.bnl.gov/viewvc/viewvc.cgi/phenix/offline/AnalysisTrain/  
PHENIXTracking_School_2021/
```

Excellent, so now you have the files, and we're ready to build. You can create build and install directories wherever you want, but it's generally good to keep your libraries and building material separate from the main directory to prevent clutter. So navigate to your build directory and type:

```
/path/to/module/autogen.sh --prefix=path/to/install/directory
```

Note that `path/to/install/directory` is typically set to `$MYINSTALL` for most people. And now in your build directory type:

```
make install -j8
```

"make install" is going to do both "make" and "make install" for us, and "-j8" just means use all available CPU cores to compile. Makes things faster. Upon completion, you should get a little message telling you shared libraries have been installed in your `$MYINSTALL` area, which means everything worked! Hooray!

4 Running the Macro

We need two files for this: `RunMyMacro.C` and `Run_Example.C`. The first contacts `Fun4All` and tells it what data to run over, and it also hands `Fun4All` `Run_Example`, which tells `Fun4All` how to analyze data with your module. I've included these in the repository, but should you need a fresh copy, they're in:

```
offline/AnalysisTrain/pat/macro
```

Which you might as well check out, because we'll be putting stuff in there later. Looking at `RunMyMacro.C` first, really the only thing you need to change is the constructor (firstly if you've changed the name of the file and secondly if you want to change the number of events or the dataset you're running over). The constructor looks like this:

```
void RunMyMacro(const char *modulemacro = "Run_Example.C",  
               const char *outfile = "out.root",  
               const int nevent = 0,  
               const char *system = "Run14AuAu200CMBPro109")
```

In order:

- `modulemacro`: `Run_Example.C`, or whatever you've renamed it as
- `outfile`: the name of our output file
- `nevent`: the number of events to run over. Note here it's 0, which means run over all available events.
- `system`: dataset, here we're looking at the Run 14 Au+Au at $\sqrt{s_{NN}} = 200\text{GeV}/c$ dataset, specifically the Central Arm, Minimum Bias data from Production 109, which include VTX information, for those interested.

Typically all you need to change is `nevent`, and I usually run it as:

```
root -l RunMyMacro.C
```

Nice and easy. But you want, you can do it this way too:

```
root -l 'RunMyMacro.C("Run_MyMacro.C", "out.root", 0, "Run14AuAu200CMBPro109")'
```

And it'll do the same thing. Again though, if you're not changing run macros or datasets very often, just do the previous command.

Cracking open Run_Example.C, the most important lines are the following:

```
gSystem->Load("libHadron_Tracking");  
Fun4AllServer *se = Fun4AllServer::instance();  
Hadron_Tracking *trkReco = new Hadron_Tracking(30., 0., 40.);  
se->registerSubsystem(trkReco);
```

- The first line tells root what unique libraries to load. Note that it's going to check in the locations in your `$LD_LIBRARY_PATH`, so you should have that setup.
- Second is simply instancing a Fun4All server to run our code
- Hadron_Tracking is our subsystem reconstruction class, so we're creating an instance of it with some initial values.
- And lastly, we register our tracking module with Fun4All so it can be used to analyze data.

5 Committing Changes to CVS

You're more than welcome to make changes to and adopt this macro for your needs. However, because this is a training module, please don't commit any changes directly to this module, especially ones that change the relevance of these instructions. If you want to use these modules as the basis for your own analysis, simply make your own Module right next to PHENIXTracking_School_2021 and copy over any files that you need. After you've added the files and whatnot, add the directory (and then the contents) with:

```
cvs add MyModule
```

Then commit it and the files with

```
cvs commit -m "Message about this commit" ObjectToBeCommitted
```

Note that cvs wants you to supply a message per commit to comment on why you're making changes. They can be super generic though like "First commit" or "Oopsie typo".

You may encounter a strange error message about permission being denied or something. If that's the case, type the following into the terminal:

```
kinit username
```

Followed by your password, then

```
aklog
```

And then you should be good to try again. And now you can use cvs to it's fullest! Oh, the last thing we need to do is rename the Run_Example.C file to something pertaining to your macro, and then copy it to

```
/offline/AnalysisTrain/pat/macro/
```

And then add and commit it to cvs from there.

6 Useful Links

Here are some useful links from the online wiki regarding this analysis:

- [This](#) is the main offline wiki page.
- [PHCentral track offline wiki](#): contains helpful information on functions from the PHCentral track class
- [EMC Cluster Container](#): At some point you're probably going to need access to EMCAL information, so you can find that here.
- [PHENIX Doxygen Page](#): details basically all the analysis classes and their functions. Overwhelming at first, but super useful once you tread into unfamiliar frameworks.

7 Submitting to the Analysis Taxi

The analysis taxi is a distributed computer cluster that's essentially one big coordinated Condor node farm. You'll submit to this when you want to make large statistics measurements over entire datasets (useful for seeing the effect of new cuts or finalizing results). There are a few things to consider before you run on the taxi though.

7.1 TNtuples and TTrees

This training module *can* for all intents and purposes be tossed on the analysis taxi to run over entire datasets. However, you really need to take stock of how much space you have (or request it in a PWG meeting if you have no space). The TNtuple that the module fills right now will essentially devour your disk space if you set it loose on Run 14's Au+Au set. TNtuple's (and their big brother, TTree's) are extremely powerful data analysis tools because they can record correlated information for a given object (in this case, all the information for a given track), but that also makes them very expensive. If you're going to run over an entire heavy ion data set, basically what you'd want to do is try breakdown information and cuts in such a way that you only fill histograms. For instance, what you're probably interested in is a charged hadron p_T spectrum at the end of the day. To make that with just a histogram, you'd settle on all your cuts, and simply toss out tracks that don't meet them at the time of analysis. This means that your analysis structure is a little more rigid, but it's the output is more light weight.

7.2 The Gatekeeper

The taxi is going to run three pieces of code over you module upon submission to make sure it can be run in a reasonable amount of time and with a reasonable amount of memory consumption.

7.2.1 cppcheck

The first and easiest to debug is cppcheck, which you'll run over the Module.h and Module.C files to check for initialization issues and such. It can be run like:

```
cppcheck --enable=all Module.C
```

And all you really care about things labelled warnings or errors. These are what will cause the Gatekeeper to reject your code. You can see from our module, we get the following:

```
[Hadron_Tracking.C:217] -> [Hadron_Tracking.C:222]: (style) Variable 'PC3matchSigma' is  
    reassigned a value before the old one has been used.  
[Hadron_Tracking.C:258]: (style) The function 'End' is never used.  
[Hadron_Tracking.C:99]: (style) The function 'Init' is never used.
```

```
[Hadron_Tracking.C:140]: (style) The function 'InitRun' is never used.
[Hadron_Tracking.C:155]: (style) The function 'process_event' is never used.
(information) Cppcheck cannot find all the include files (use --check-config for details)
```

All of these are marked “style,” so they don’t really matter. Be sure to check the header file as well! It’s going to tell you “using namespace std” is invalid C code, and there are some reasons not to use that command, but typing `std::` everywhere is annoying and ultimately the Gatekeeper doesn’t care.

7.2.2 Valgrind

The big chungus of the Gatekeeper. This is going to check for memory leaks by running over your code with a fine toothed comb, so it takes upwards of 2-3 times the normal run time. Because of that, make sure you only run over about 100 events, or you’ll be waiting for hours. However, you might implement some processes (such as event mixing) that will only start after say, 500 events have passed. Any code that doesn’t activate until after 500 events won’t be checked by Valgrind, so you need to use enough events that all your code gets checked. The Gatekeeper will pass your module about 300,000 events, so don’t worry about that. Valgrind’s run command is pretty complicated, so it’s way easier to create an alias like this:

```
alias VALG valgrind -v --num-callers=40 --leak-check=full --error-limit=no \
    --log-file=valgrind.log --suppressions=$ROOTSYS/root.supp \
    --leak-resolution=high --track-origins=yes root.exe
```

Then you just type:

```
VALG
```

Followed by

```
.x RunMyMacro.C
```

And out of this you’ll get your regular root output file (so be sure to rename your last one if it’s important), and a `valgrind.log` file. Now, if you’re lucky (which I hope I am since I’m doing these checks as I write this), you should be able to just do

```
tail valgrind.log
```

Which will show you the last like, five lines of the output, and it will show you:

```
/afs/rhic.bnl.gov/phenix/PHENIX_LIB/sys/x8664_s17/ana.653/root/root.supp:1199
--7448-- used_suppression: 1 <insert_a_suppression_name_here> /afs/rhic.bnl.gov/phenix/PHENIX_LIB
/sys/x8664_s17/ana.653/root/root.supp:88
--7448-- used_suppression: 1 <insert_a_suppression_name_here> /afs/rhic.bnl.gov/phenix/PHENIX_LIB
/sys/x8664_s17/ana.653/root/root.supp:286
==7448==
==7448== ERROR SUMMARY: 0 errors from 0 contexts (suppressed: 58316 from 352)
```

And that’s what we’re looking for! “0 errors from 0 contexts” means our code has passed Valgrind. Now it’s time to use

7.2.3 Insure

Insure is really the same procedure as valgrind. We’re going to run our code over a small set of data to see if it runs efficiently. This alias

```
alias INSU unsetenv OFFLINE_MAIN\
    unsetenv ONLINE_MAIN\
    unsetenv ROOTSYS\
    cp -p $ROOTSYS/insure.psrc .psrc\
    source /opt/phenix/bin/phenix_setup.csh new+insure\
```

Then do

```
root_insure.exe
```

And again run your module. This time it'll spit out an insure.report, which you can tail just like the valgrind output, and it should say something like this:

```
READ_WILD: Reading wild pointer, 2 unique occurrences
  781 at PC: 0xf6b1c330
    1 at PC: 0xf726d014
```

No leaks were found.

“No leaks were found” means we're good to go! And we're ready to submit to the taxi.

7.3 Submitting Your Job

The analysis taxi page submission page can be found [here](#). It's really just a series of boxes to check like your username and the location of your macros (which need to be committed to CVS to be able to be read mind you). Then you tick the box of whatever data set you want. If you scroll all the way down to the bottom you can see the Run 14 data set, and we'd select the box next to:

```
Run-14 200 GeV Au+Au pro106 (MinBias)
```

Or, if you need VTX support:

```
Run-14 200 GeV Au+Au pro109 (MinBias)
```

You'll notice that it has some other information next to it, like the quoted ~ 19 billion events, and these:

```
DSTs: CNT, DST_EVE, DST_MPC
```

And those just mean the data set types that are available. For our intents and purposes, we're interested in the CNT (CeNTral arm) set. And then down at the bottom we have some other options:

- DST Types: explained right above. There are tons of them, though, but you'll learn which ones mean what when you need them.
- Aggregation: Here's a very coarse breakdown of PHENIX Data: Run Number(year 1-16) -> runnumber (many thousands) -> run_segment (many more thousands of files). So aggregation combines all the segments into one file for a given runnumber, say run 414507 in Run 14. This is really just to make your life easier, since HADD'ing tens of thousands of files takes literal days.
- Event Mixing/Embedding: Don't worry about this for now. Basically mixing data sets to isolate certain effects.
- Runnumber list: Like I was saying above how the different Runs are broken down into different runnumbers, you can enter a list of them here. The detector's status changes runnumber by runnumber (say a pigeon collides with the drift chamber, oof), and you might want to exclude some runs. Thus you'd create a "good run list" and put it in this box. Yes, all however many hundreds of runs go into that box. Just trust me. Or leave it blank to run over everything. You'll probably have to do this first to see what each run looks like.
- Estimated disc space: Doesn't actually do anything, but it's good to know this and the amount of storage you have left, or else the taxi will crash.
- Additional Requests: I'm pretty sure no one reads this, so just put a smiley face and maybe Chris Pinkenburg will see it.

And that's it and you can hit submit! You'll either be taken to a success page or a page that tells you something you forgot to enter. Just hit the back button and try again.

8 Analyzing Data from Our Module

Okay okay okay! We've built our macro, run it, gatekeeper'd it, and tossed it on the taxi (well maybe you did, we're only going to use disc-resident statistics in the tutorial), but now we'd like to actually analyze the data we got out. Let's take a look at the macros in the macros directory. Your module directory should have a macros directory, and it's important that it's named "macros". The analysis taxi will ignore this area when it's time to compile things, and including a macros directory is now required for the purpose of documentation.

The macros directory comes with two analysis macros: DrawTracking.C and DrawNTuple.C. The first is to draw the 3-dimensional histograms we filled on the train, and the second makes plots from the TNTuple we filled. Now, DrawTracking.C isn't going to run like RunMyMacro because there's no function in it called "DrawTracking". It's more like a library that contains three functions: DrawDCH, DrawPC3Dead, and DrawEMCDead, and each of them takes in output from the train/RunMyMacro.C. To run any of the functions, do the following:

```
root -l
.L DrawTracking
DrawDCH("../se-out.root")
```

And that will work for DrawNTuple as well, you'd just use "DrawNTuple("../se-out.root")" for the last line. DrawNTuple.C also contains a little worksheet for you to attempt focusing on drawing various histograms derived from the TNTuple. The two plots below are drawn by DrawTracking.C's DrawDCH function and DrawNTuple.C, respectively. Note that this is just from a disc resident file, so don't draw too many conclusions from the limited statistics.

Figure 1: Map of tracks reconstructed in the drift chamber separated into various p_T bins

Inclusive Track p_T

Figure 2: p_T distribution for all tracks that pass basic sanity cuts from the analysis macro